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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **OL**ive and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 6.13

Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.4

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All partners involved in the production/implementation of the deliverable should comment and report (if needed) in the above table. The above table should support the decisions made for the specific deliverable in order to include the agreement of all involved parties for the final version of the document.

Finally, after the peer review process, the deliverable should be modified accordingly to the comments and the reflections to the comments should be reported in the above table.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report gives an update on work summarised in D6.12, which described interactions between MED-GOLD and other initiatives as part of task 6.1. This task specifically is pursuing dissemination synergies with other EU initiatives such as Climate-KIC, JPI Climate, FACE-JPI, JPI Water and related ERA-NET (e.g. ERA-NET on Climate Services) as well as clustering with other climate service-related EC funded projects via H2020 or other complementary programmes (e.g. LIFE, Copernicus, PRIMA, etc.). There is also a focus on getting involved with other agriculture-related initiatives that include a significant climate component.

- MED-GOLD partners were approached and asked to summarise any existing interactions with other projects and possible new interactions. They were also asked to summarise abstracts submitted to forthcoming conferences.
- MED-GOLD partners have contacts with many other projects, as they are either partners on those projects, or have established informal links with certain institutions.
- This deliverable focuses on the period December 2020 to November 2021.
- There were no deviations from the DoA.

1. OBJECTIVES

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, Part B Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

2. IMPACT

Please describe briefly how this deliverable contributes to the relevant expected impacts of the work programme

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value-added climate services in potential end-user markets	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1 - Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Climate Services	The provision of climate information in such a way as to assist decision-making.

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 2 - Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ADAPT2CLIMA	Adaptation to Climate Change Impacts on the Mediterranean islands' Agriculture
AfriCultuRes	Enhancing Food Security in African AgriCultural Systems with the support of Remote Sensing
AgMIP	The Agricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project
Agri Adapt	Sustainable adaptation of typical EU farming systems to climate change
AgroSat	Satellite data for agriculture in Italy
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputacion
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Services
CAFE	Climate Advanced Forecasting of sub-seasonal Extremes
CEEV	Comité Européen des Entreprises Vins
DATI	Digital Agriculture Technologies for Irrigation efficiency
EASME	Executive Agency for SMEs
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
ERA	European Research Area (e.g., ERA-NET)
H2020	Horizon 2020
JPI	Joint Programming Initiative
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MEDCLIV	Mediterranean Climate Vine & Wine Ecosystem
MedECC	Mediterranean Experts on Climate and environmental Change
MED-GOLD	Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems
MEDSCOPE	MEDiterranean Services Chain based On climate PrEdictions
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
PRIMA	Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area
S2S4E	Sub-seasonal to Seasonal climate forecasting for Energy
SECLI-FIRM	The Added Value of Seasonal Climate Forecasts for Integrated Risk Management Decisions

SYSTEMIC	An integrated approach to the challenge of sustainable food systems: adaptive and mitigation strategies to address climate change and malnutrition
TEBEKA	Territory Basic Knowledge Acquisition
VITIGEOSS	Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 3 - References

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.1	D6.1	2.0	01-12-2018
[RD.2]	Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.2	D6.11	1.5	01-12-2019
[RD.3]	Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.3	D6.12	1.4	01-12-2020

6. DETAILED REPORT

6.1. STATE OF THE ART

A wide range of innovative projects on climate services and agriculture are underway. Many partners on MED-GOLD coordinate, or are participants, in some of these projects, and have established formal and informal links with other projects. These links allow ideas from MED-GOLD to be promoted, and earlier on, new results from other projects were incorporated into MED-GOLD.

6.2 METHODS

MED-GOLD project partners were approached and asked to summarise projects related to climate services and agriculture that they are involved with, either as coordinators or partners. They were also asked to describe other initiatives that could be of interest to MED-GOLD, or those that might benefit from links with MED-GOLD. Finally, partners provided titles of presentations given at conferences and workshops where MED-GOLD was promoted, or results were discussed.

This report only summarises projects and other initiatives which were active between November 2020 and November 2021. Other initiatives in which MED-GOLD partners were involved but have ended were summarised in the previous reports ([RD.1], [RD.2] and [RD.3]).

6.3 MAIN RESULTS

Projects and initiatives are divided into those concerned with the development of climate services, and those more closely focused on agriculture. The first two tables (4 and 5) describe projects that MED-GOLD partners are already working with, either as project leads or partners. The next two tables (6 and 7) summarise projects with less direct links, where MED-GOLD partners have been invited to present results, or had informal conversations. Table 8 briefly mentions international conferences, workshops and in-country events where partners have presented (or will present) results from MED-GOLD.

6.2.1 DESCRIPTION OF INITIATIVES RELATED TO CLIMATE SERVICES WE ARE WORKING WITH

MED-GOLD partners are involved in many other projects involving the provision of climate services, which are listed in Table 4. These projects cover a wide range of subjects, from the use of seasonal and decadal forecasts to more general knowledge integration and dissemination.

Table 4 - Description of initiatives related to climate services that MED-GOLD is working with

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact

C3S_34c_DWD (Prototype Service for Decadal Climate Predictions)	C3S	The contract has developed a prototype about the use of decadal predictions in the agriculture sector. https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:606594-2019:TEXT:EN:HTML	Ended in June 2021.	BSC and JRC were partners on this project. Joint publication with participation of MED-GOLD and EUCP.	BSC, JRC
Climate-KIC (Knowledge and Innovation Community)		Climate-KIC is a European knowledge and innovation community, working to accelerate the transition to a zero-carbon economy. Supported by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT). http://www.climate-kic.org/	Ongoing	Some informal contacts	ENEA, Univ Leeds
Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)		http://www.copernicus.eu/ Includes a global agriculture project that may be of interest/use. https://climate.copernicus.eu/global-agriculture-project	Ongoing	Met Office are partners in C3S.	ENEA, Met Office, Beetobit
EC Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA)		Institution that leads the European Commission's efforts to fight climate change at EU and international level. https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action_en	Ongoing	Policy officer of DG CLIMA invited BSC to attend a general discussion about the work done in different climate services related projects (MED-GOLD among them).	BSC
EUCP (European Climate Prediction System)	H2020	Project with the goal of producing actionable climate information for risk-based planning. It develops cutting-edge approaches to using climate predictions and projections, as well as providing new climate simulations, never rolled out before on a European level. This lays the foundation for a future regional climate prediction system for Europe. The project has developed a	Ongoing	Met Office is the project coordinator. BSC is a partner on this project. Joint publication with participation of MED-GOLD and EUCP.	Met Office, BSC

		<p>storyline for the agriculture sector.</p> <p>https://www.eucp-project.eu/</p>			
Indecis	ERA4CS / ERA-NET / JPI	<p>Indecis is concerned with the development across Europe of user-oriented climate indicators for GFCS high-priority sectors: agriculture, disaster risk reduction, energy, health, water and tourism.</p> <p>http://www.indecis.eu/</p>	Finished (June 2021)	BSC are partners on Indecis.	BSC
MEDSCOPE	ERA4CS	<p>MEDSCOPE is working on optimisation of seasonal forecasts of Mediterranean region, this is possibly of interest for MED-GOLD</p> <p>https://www.medscope-project.eu/</p>	Finished (June 2021)	BSC are partners on MEDSCOPE.	BSC
S2S4E (Sub-seasonal to Seasonal climate forecasting for Energy)	H2020	<p>S2S4E will offer an innovative service to improve renewable energy (RE) variability management by developing new research methods exploring the frontiers of weather conditions for future weeks and months.</p> <p>https://s2s4e.eu/</p>	Finished	Developing case studies for different energy related sectors as well as a visualization platform with sub-seasonal and seasonal climate predictions that can provide some ideas to MED-GOLD.	BSC (coordinators), ENEA

SECLI-FIRM The added value of Seasonal Climate Forecasts for Integrated Risk Management Decisions)	H2020	The central objective of SECLI-FIRM is to demonstrate how the use of improved climate forecasts, out to several months ahead, can add practical and economic value to decision-making processes and outcomes, primarily in the energy sector, but also in the water sector. http://www.secli-firm.eu/	Finished. Final conference took place on 13, 14 and 19 October 2021.	Met Office and ENEA were partners on this project. SOGRAPE presented MED-GOLD climate services for wine at workshop on May 25, 2021.	Met Office, ENEA
WCRP Grand Challenge on Near-Term Climate Prediction		The Grand Challenge on Near-Term Climate Prediction will support research and development to improve multi-year to decadal climate predictions and their utility to decision makers. It will furthermore support the development of organizational and technical processes for future routine provision of decadal prediction services that can assist stakeholders and decision-makers. https://www.wcrp-climate.org/grand-challenges/grand-challenges-overview	Finished (June 2021)	Met Office is a partner on this project.	Met Office

6.2.2 DESCRIPTION OF EACH AGRICULTURAL INITIATIVE WITH WHICH WE ARE WORKING

MED-GOLD partners are involved in a wide range of different agricultural initiatives (Table 5). These projects include the improved use of multiple satellite data products for agricultural monitoring and planning, improved water use, and knowledge exchange and capacity building. For some other projects in Table 5, the links are more informal, and exist where MED-GOLD partners were invited to workshops to present results.

Table 5 - Description of each agricultural initiative with which we are already working

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact
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<p>AgroSat (Satellite data for Agriculture in Italy)</p>	<p>Copernicus</p>	<p>AgroSat combines digital technologies (IoT and Big Data) and scientific research products to create a direct connection between research, farmers and food/feed companies. AgroSat is a Copernicus Use Case.</p> <p>https://www.copernicus.eu/en/use-cases/agrosat</p> <p>It is an open source platform that redistributes Copernicus Sentinels and CLGS SWI for all Italian arable areas. Historical data are available for the last four years in terms of vegetation index, RGB and soil moisture, providing on-the-fly precision maps for chemical applications and maps for potential yield estimates.</p>	<p>Ongoing</p>	<p>The seasonal forecast (Biased and Unbiased) used as input for Delphi model. Test and benchmark assessed and redistributed by AgroSat to the end user (Barilla).</p>	<p>CNR, Barilla</p>
<p>CEEV (Comité Européen des Entreprises Vins)</p>		<p>Representative body of the EU Industry and trade in wines.</p> <p>https://www.ceev.eu/</p>	<p>Ongoing</p>	<p>The Secretary General of strategic orientation, representation, press relations and daily management gave an invited talk during the MED-GOLD General Assembly 2019.</p>	<p>ENEA, SOGRAPE</p>
<p>COPA-COGECA</p>		<p>Lobby organization representing agricultural cooperatives. They are participating in the design and development of public European policies.</p> <p>https://copa-cogeca.eu</p>	<p>Ongoing</p>	<p>Prof. Anna Rufolo is a member of the external advisory committee of MED-GOLD.</p> <p>Policy advisors for the wine and olive sector participated in an interview to discuss how MED-GOLD results could be useful for the policy community.</p>	<p>BSC, ENEA</p>

DATI (Digital Agriculture Technologies for Irrigation efficiency)	PRIMA	DATI aims to design and develop new Digital Agriculture (DA) technological solutions and procedures for crop and soil monitoring with the purpose of optimizing irrigation management by improving irrigation equipment at the farm scale and scheduling water release according to crop needs. https://www.utad.pt/gap/dati/	Ongoing	CNR are partners on DATI.	CNR
e-crops	MISE – The Ministry of Economic Development in Italy	The E-crops project is a public-private interdisciplinary project aimed at digital agriculture, led by CNR and composed of four public and ten private entities. http://www.ponricerca.gov.it/comunicazione/example-projects/industrial-research-and-experimental-development-projects-in-the-12-specialization-areas/e-crops-technology-for-sustainable-digital-agriculture/	Ongoing	CNR is leading the project and Sandro Calmanti (ENEA) is a member of the Advisory Board.	CNR, ENEA
Evoinos (The Heritage Project, Cyprus Wine Project)		Evoinos strives for knowledge and capacity building through advocacy, cultural management to engage and inspire diverse professional and non-professional wine loving audiences. https://evoinos.com/	Ongoing	The Twitter accounts @evoinos and MED-GOLD follow each other. This project also has Instagram and Facebook presence through which we can connect. Info@evoinos.com	Through social media
FOCUS-Africa (Full-value chain Optimised Climate User-centric Services for Southern Africa)	H2020	Aim: to develop sustainable tailored climate services in the Southern African Development Community to illustrate how the application of new climate forecasts, projections and resources from Copernicus, GFCS and other relevant products can maximise socio-economic benefits in the Southern Africa region and potentially in the whole of Africa.	Started September 2020	BSC and JRC are partners on this project. Joint publication with participation of MED-GOLD and FOCUS-Africa.	BSC, JRC

		<p>Agriculture and food security is one of the four sectors targeted.</p> <p>https://focus-africaproject.eu/</p>			
<p>PRIMA (Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area)</p>	H2020	<p>A joint programme focused on the development and application of solutions for food systems and water resources in the Mediterranean basin.</p> <p>http://ec.europa.eu/research/environment/index.cfm?pg=prima</p>	Ongoing	PRIMA coordinator is a member of the MED-GOLD External Advisory Committee.	ENEA
<p>SYSTEMIC (An integrated approach to the challenge of sustainable food systems: adaptive and mitigation strategies to address climate change and malnutrition)</p>	ERA - HDHL	<p>The SYSTEMIC network gathers the excellence of existing research in livestock, crop production, aquaculture, climate change, nutrition, consumption, consumer behaviour, society, and environmental health to explore cross-cutting solutions, identify knowledge gaps and develop a pathway for food system transformation, which is climate-resilient and able to cope with societal challenges.</p> <p>http://systemic-hub.eu/</p>	Ongoing	CNR is a partner of the SYSTEMIC project hub, specifically in Task1.1 (Climate change scenarios and data needs) of WP1 (Resource use, current knowledge, and future trends).	CNR
<p>TEBAKA (TErritorial BASic Knowledge Acquisition)</p>		<p>Industrial research project funded by European structural and investment funds. The project will design and prototype a network-based service for farmers to provide them with an easy and economically viable source of information to support improved crop management, with optimized cost / benefit ratio.</p> <p>https://www.dtascarl.org/en/progetti/tebaka/</p>	Ongoing	TEBAKA is explicitly linked to MED-GOLD, and focuses on the same set of Mediterranean crop systems, with a focus on the Italian region of Puglia.	ENEA

Tierras De Mollina		Comprises 600 cooperatives, 844 ha of vineyards, producing 80% of musts and wines under the designation 'origin Malaga'. https://www.tierrasdemollina.com/	Ongoing	The Twitter accounts @VinosdeMollina and @medgold_H2020 follow each other. This might be a good option for future workshop invitations: vitivinicola@virgendelaoliva.com	Through social media
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6.2.3 DESCRIPTION OF INITIATIVES RELATED TO CLIMATE SERVICES FOR POSSIBLE FUTURE INTERACTIONS

Projects related to development and provision of climate services, but are not directly relevant to MED-GOLD, are summarised in Table 6. These projects are focused on countries outside of Europe, or topics not explicitly covered by MED-GOLD (for example, climate extremes). In some cases, MED-GOLD partners work on these projects. For others, MED-GOLD results have been disseminated by other projects.

Table 6 - Description of initiatives related to climate services for possible future interactions

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact
AfriCultuRes (Enhancing Food Security in African AgriCultural Systems with the support of Remote Sensing)	H2020	To design, implement and demonstrate an integrated agricultural monitoring and early warning system that will support decision making in the field of food security. http://www.africultures.eu/	Ongoing	Preliminary conversations held. In a second meeting GMV explained the services offered by MED-GOLD. The AfriCultuRes coordinator was interested in some examples of replicability. PBDM applied to armyworm in Maize crops. A third meeting is on the table.	GMV (project coordinators)
BLUE-ACTION (Arctic impact on weather and climate)	H2020	Project on Arctic impact on climate and weather. https://blue-action.eu/	Finished (September 2021)	The Twitter accounts @BG10Blueaction and @medgold_H2020 follow each other. Coordinator: Steffen M. Olsen DMI smo@dmi.dk	Via social media

CAFÉ (Climate Advanced Forecasting of sub-seasonal Extremes)	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network	Project focused on climate extremes http://www.cafes2se-itn.eu/	Ongoing	Showing interest in collaborating with MED-GOLD.	BSC
CLIMAGRI	Life programme	Conservation agriculture. Irrigation. Adaptation and mitigation of climate change. Soil loss. http://climagri.eu/index.php/en/	Ongoing	None so far.	DCOOP
Climate-ADAPT		Platform from the European Commission and the European Environment Agency to share adaptation information across Europe. https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/	Ongoing	Climate-ADAPT invited the MED-GOLD project to submit news or events to be published on their website and potentially in one of their regular newsletters.	ENEA, BSC, GMV
ISlpedia	ERA4CS/ JPI Climate	ISlpedia will be an online portal for national-level, cross-sectoral climate-impact assessments, based on state-of-the-art climate-impacts simulations from ISIMIP. ISlpedia will include a new round of ISIMIP climate-impacts simulations. The focus topic of the simulation round will be decided upon in consultation with relevant interest groups and stakeholders. Stakeholders will also contribute to designing the ISlpedia web portal, including the content of the impact assessments. https://www.isimip.org/isipedia/	Ongoing	Inga Menke inga.menke@climateanalytics.org Quentin Lejeune quentin.lejeune@climateanalytics.org The Twitter accounts @ISI_pedia and @medgold_H2020 follow each other.	Via social media
MEDCLIV (Mediterranean Climate Vine & Wine Ecosystem)	CLIMATE-KIC	Builds collaborative platform for climate change in the Mediterranean.	A partner attended the Living Lab in 2020.	emanuele.eccel@fmach.it MEDCLIV survey addressing users' needs in the agriculture sector was	

				disseminated in one of the MED-GOLD newsletters.	
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6.2.4 DESCRIPTION OF INITIATIVES RELATED TO AGRICULTURE FOR POSSIBLE FUTURE INTERACTIONS

Table 7 summarises projects related to agriculture, but are not directly relevant to MED-GOLD. Many of these projects aim to provide key information to improve crop management using a variety of different information sources. In most cases, MED-GOLD partners have made informal links, via presenting results or other interactions.

Table 7 - Description of initiatives related to agriculture for possible future interactions

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact
AgMIP (Agricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project)	Global UK/US government funded initiative	Major international effort linking the climate, crop, and economic modelling communities supported by UK Department for International Development's UKAid, in partnership with the US Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service http://www.agmip.org/	Ongoing	Prof. Bruno Basso (Michigan State University, USA) is a member of the MED-GOLD External Advisory Committee. Under AgMIP, the Met Office develops crop models which have been used to provide seasonal forecasts of carbon uptake by vegetation and the wildfire risk, as well as longer term projections of climate impacts on crops.	ENEA, Met Office

Cenecafé		<p>A climate network for coffee growers in Colombia which is supported by Federacafe. It has online access with useful climate information for producers.</p> <p>They publish the “Anuario Meterológico Cafetero” compiling the annual climate information from numerous ground stations, all located in traditional coffee growing areas. They provided general information about best planting dates in different regions of Colombia and rain forecast.</p> <p>https://agroclima.cenicaf e.org/</p>	Ongoing	<p>MED-GOLD partners in Colombia have interacted with various people within Cenecafé.</p>	Universidad Militar
Global Agriculture Sectoral Information System	Copernicus	<p>A project funded by the European Commission designed to support society by providing authoritative information about the past, present and future climate for adaptation and mitigation purposes by providing consistent and authoritative information about climate change. Their Climate Data Store offers free and open access to climate data and tools.</p> <p>http://www.copernicus.e u/</p>	Ongoing	<p>Copernicus has a global agriculture project as part of this, which may be of interest/use.</p> <p>https://climate.copernicus.eu/g lobal-agriculture-project</p>	Met Office

MedECC (Mediterranean Experts on Climate and environmental Change)	UNEP, Union for the Mediterranean	MedECC is a network of scientists working towards a regional science-policy interface for climatic and other environmental changes across the Mediterranean. https://www.medecc.org	Ongoing	ENEA gave a presentation on the use of climate data within MED-GOLD at a workshop “Data for climate action in the Mediterranean”, 25-26 October 2021.	ENEA
SUSTAIN OLIVE	PRIMA	The main goal of SUSTAINOLIVE is to improve the sustainability of the olive oil sector, through the implementation and promotion of a set of innovative sustainable management solutions, based on agro-ecological concepts, as well as in the exchange of knowledge and participation of multiple associates and end users. https://sustainolive.eu/?lang=en	Ongoing	Coordinators approached to join the MED-GOLD community.	DCOOP
VITIGEOSS (Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors)	H2020	Aims to create an innovative commercial information delivery to optimize sustainable vine cultivation via decision support systems (DSS) on phenology, irrigation, fertilizer, disease and business operations management. https://vitigeoss.eu/	Started September 2020	BSC participating as partner. Uses indicator created in MED-GOLD (harvest total precipitation). Developed a dashboard integrating various intelligent services, one of them on weather and climate forecasts. VITIGEOSS survey disseminated through one of the MED-GOLD newsletters.	BSC

6.2.5 EVENTS THAT ARE OF POSSIBLE INTEREST FOR MAKING NEW CONTACTS.

Table 8 lists conferences, workshops and other events where results from MED-GOLD have been or could be promoted and useful contacts made. Note that some events have been either postponed or cancelled owing to the Covid-19 pandemic.

Table 8 - Events that are of possible interest for making new contacts

Title	Date	Location	Other Info	Audience and project members attending?
EGU2021	25 - 30 April 2021	Online	https://www.egu2021.eu/	<p>ENEA gave a presentation "MED-GOLD Living Lab 2020: the story of an online training event".</p> <p>NOA presented a poster "Return period analysis to assess the long-term impact of climate change on olive sector in Andalusia, Spain - results from the Med-Gold project".</p>
Met Office Climate Science Conference	11-12 May 2021	Online	https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/news/conferences/met-office-science-conference	Met Office presented a poster giving an overview of the MED-GOLD Dashboard.
EMS Annual Meeting	6-10 September 2021	Online	https://www.ems2021.eu/home.html	<p>BSC gave an oral presentation "Understanding climate and non-climate decision triggers to minimize spring rainfall risks in vineyards", https://doi.org/10.5194/ems2021-489</p>
SPIE Remote Sensing	13-16 September 2021	Madrid, Spain	https://spie.org/conferences-and-exhibitions/remote-sensing	GMV gave an oral presentation, "Satellite imagery and climate variables suggest variations in the phenology of olive groves in Southern Spain." (Paper number 11856-24).
9th SISC Annual Conference "Accelerating Climate Action: A just transition in a post-Covid era"	22-24 September 2021	Online	https://www.sisclima.it/conferenza-annuale-2021/?lang=en	ENEA presented a poster, "Overcoming conflicting notions of climate forecasts reliability and skill in the agricultural sector: lessons from the MED-GOLD project."
EXPOLIVIA 2021. XX International Fair of the Olive Oil and Allied Industries.	22 - 25 September 2021	Jaén, Spain	http://www.expoliva.com/expoliva2021/	DCOOP distributed a brochure describing MED-GOLD to attendees and explained the project

				and its objectives (informally).
Data for climate action in the Mediterranean	25-26 October 2021	Online	https://climate.copernicus.eu/data-climate-action-mediterranean	ENEA were invited to give a short talk on MED-GOLD.
AGU Fall Meeting	13-17 December 2021	New Orleans, Los Angeles and online	https://www.agu.org/Fall-Meeting	Includes a session devoted to the AgMIP project.
7th International Congress of Mountain and Steep Slopes Viticulture	Postponed to May 2022. Pre-congress event held on 13 th May 2021.	Vila Real, Portugal, and online.	https://viicongresscervim.utad.pt/index.aspx Postponed from 2020	Researchers, consultants, technical staff, farmers.
EGU 2022	3-8 April 2022	Vienna and online (hybrid)	https://www.egu22.eu	Several MED-GOLD contributions are expected in the Climate services session: https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU22/session/42621
14th International Terroir Congress and the 2nd ClimWine Congress	3-8 July 2022	Talence, Bordeaux	https://terclim2022.symposium.inrae.fr/	Sogrape and ENEA have submitted an abstract: "Is wine terroir a valid notion under a changing climate?"
International Cool Climate Wine Symposium	Postponed to 17-21 July 2022	Brock University, Ontario, Canada	http://iccws2020.ca/ Postponed from 2020	Scientists, consultants, policy-makers, entrepreneurs, technicians, students.

7. EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

The tables in sections 6.2.1 to 6.2.5 summarise a wide range of projects that MED-GOLD partners are participating in, have established links with, or at least aware of. These links allow results and ideas to be communicated between MED-GOLD and other projects, to avoid replication of work and improve overall results.

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